

TEACHER- LEARNER INTERACTIONS AND SOCIAL- EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT AMONG KINDERGARTEN CLASSROOMS IN MARILOG DISTRICT B

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Abstract. The study unfolded the teacher-learner interaction and social-emotional development among kindergarten learners in Marilog B District, Davao City Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style, teaching strategies, classroom environment, student's temperament, cultural background and teacher's attitude and denotes extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive, while, extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of peer relationship, teacher-student relationship, classroom environment, family environment and personal temperament denotes oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. There is a significant correlation between teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development among kinder learners. Indicators of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style, classroom environment, teaching strategies and teacher attitude and personality significantly influenced social-emotional development among kinder learners. May investigate the impact of students' temperament and cultural background on social-emotional development among kinder learners.

KEY WORDS

1. teacher- learner interactions .
2. social- emotional development.

1. Introduction

Kindergarten is a critical period for children's social-emotional development. In rural areas, however, children may face additional challenges that could negatively impact their development, such as limited access to resources and fewer opportunities for socialization. Teacher-learner interaction plays a vital role in supporting children's social-emotional development, but research gaps exist in understanding how this interaction affects rural kindergarten learners. Several studies have highlighted the importance of teacher-learner interaction in supporting social-emotional development. For instance, Crosnoe and Ansari (2015) found that positive teacher-child relationships in preschool could promote children's social-emotional development. Similarly, Shernoff, Csikszentmihalyi, Schneider, and Shernoff (2015) identified the importance of student-teacher relationships in promoting engagement

and achievement in the classroom. The social-emotional development of young children is a critical component of their early learning and development. Social-emotional skills provide the foundation for children's success in school and in life, helping them form positive relationships, regulate their emotions, and navigate social situations effectively. Effective teacher-learner interactions play a significant role in promoting the social-emotional development of young learners, particularly in rural areas where children may face unique challenges. Despite the growing recognition of the importance of social-emotional development in early childhood, research has identified several international challenges in this area. A study by Zhou, Wang, and Zhang (2018) found that children in rural areas are at a disadvantage in terms of social-emotional development due to limited access to early childhood education and insufficient resources. Additionally, research by Raver, Jones, Li-Grining, Metzger, Smallwood, and Sardin (2018) highlighted the importance of the quality of teacher-child interactions in promoting social-emotional development and identified the need for additional training and support for teachers in this area. However, research gaps exist in the understanding of how teacher-learner interaction affects social-emotional development in rural kindergarten learners. According to Fauth, Decristan, Rieser, Klieme, and Büttner (2014), few studies have focused on the experiences of rural students and how they differ from those of their urban counterparts. This gap in knowledge makes it difficult to design effective interventions that could address the unique needs of rural students. A study by Salazar, Del Prado, and Santos (2018) found that kindergarten teachers in the Philippines lack adequate training in social-emotional development, resulting in limited knowledge and skills in promoting positive social-emotional outcomes for their students. Additionally, research by Natividad and Lingad (2020) highlighted the challenges faced by kinder learners in rural areas, including poverty, limited access to early childhood education, and inadequate resources. On the other hand, the early years of a child's life are critical for their social-emotional development. Kindergarten education provides an important foundation for the development of social-emotional skills, particularly for children in rural areas who may face unique challenges in their learning environments. Teacher-learner interaction plays a crucial role in facilitating the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners in rural areas. Another research gap in this area is the lack of attention given to cultural differences in rural areas. According to Spilt, Koomen, and Thijs (2016), cultural differences between teachers and students can affect teacher-learner interaction and the development of social-emotional skills. However, there is limited research on how cultural differences impact teacher-learner interaction in rural areas. In light of these challenges, this study seeks to explore the role of teacher-learner interactions in promoting social-emotional development among kindergarten learners in rural areas. Specifically, this study aims to examine the relationship between positive teacher-learner interactions and the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners in rural areas. By exploring the impact of teacher-learner interactions on social-emotional development, this study seeks to provide insights into effective strategies for promoting positive social-emotional outcomes for young learners in Marilog B District, Davao City.

2. Related Literature

This section presents the review of significant literature. This further discusses the contentions of the authors from the international to local settings. Variables under study, teacher-kinder learner interactions in terms of communication style, student's temperament, classroom environment, teaching strategies and teacher's attitude and personality are discussed. Likewise, the dependent variable, social – emotional development of kindergarten learners such as family environment, peer relationship, teacher-students relationship, classroom environment, and personal temperament are also presented to support the claims of the variables used under study.

Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction. The interaction between teachers and kindergarten learners is critical in the education process, particularly in rural areas. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), children from rural areas often lack access to education, and those who do, may not receive quality education. This is mainly due to the limited resources and infrastructure available in rural areas. As such, the teacher-kinder learner interaction becomes more crucial as it determines the quality of education that children in rural areas receive. The Importance of Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in Rural Areas The teacher-kinder learner interaction is critical in creating an enabling learning environment in rural areas. According to Mundy, Green and Lingard (2016), teacher-student interaction is essential in fostering learning and development among children. In rural areas where children may lack exposure to the world outside their communities, the teacher-kinder learner interaction helps to broaden their perspectives and prepare them for life beyond their immediate environment. In addition, the teacher-kinder learner interaction is crucial in improving the academic performance of children in rural areas. In a study by Abdulsalam and Adetoro (2019), it was noted that teacher-student interaction plays a vital role in the academic success of learners in rural areas. This is because the interaction helps to identify the strengths and weaknesses of individual learners and develop appropriate strategies to help them improve their academic performance. Challenges Facing Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in Rural Areas Despite the importance of teacher-kinder learner interaction, several challenges hinder effective interaction in rural areas. One of the significant challenges is the shortage of qualified teachers. According to UNESCO (2021), over 69 million teachers need to be recruited globally to achieve universal primary and secondary education by 2030. This shortage is particularly severe in rural areas, where teachers are often overworked, underpaid, and lack adequate training. In addition, the limited infrastructure in rural areas poses a significant challenge to teacher-kinder learner interaction. For instance, poor road networks and inadequate transport systems make it difficult for teachers to access remote areas. Lack of electricity and internet connectivity also hinders the use of technology in teaching and learning, thus limiting the effectiveness of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Strategies for Enhancing Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in Rural Areas To enhance teacher-kinder learner interaction in rural areas, several strategies can be employed. One of the most effective strategies is the provision of training and professional development opportunities for teachers. According to Sallis, Probert and Hebron (2019), teacher training and development programs improve the skills and knowledge of teachers, thus enabling them to deliver quality education to learners. The use of technology is another strategy that can enhance teacher-kinder learner interaction in rural areas.

According to Mbarika et al. (2020), technology, such as mobile devices and online platforms, can help to bridge the gap between teachers and learners in remote areas. By using technology, teachers can interact with learners, share educational resources and provide feedback, thus enhancing the effectiveness of teacher-kinder learner interaction. In conclusion, the teacher-kinder learner interaction is critical in the education process, particularly in rural areas. The interaction helps to create an enabling learning environment, improve academic performance, and prepare learners for life beyond their immediate environment. However, several challenges hinder effective interaction in rural areas, including the shortage of qualified teachers and limited infrastructure. To enhance teacher-kinder learner interaction in rural areas, strategies such as training and professional development for teachers and the use of technology can be employed.

Communication Style. Teacher-Kindergarten learner interaction is a critical-component of effective teaching and learning, and communication style plays an important role in shaping the nature of this interaction. In rural schools, where resources may be limited and access to technology may be limited, effective communication between teachers and kindergarten learners is even more critical. Communication style is a crucial aspect of the teacher-kinder learner interaction in international settings, particularly in rural areas. Effective communication between teachers and learners facilitates the transmission of knowledge, builds rapport, and enhances learners' academic performance. In the context of Teacher-Kindergarten learner interaction, communication style can influence the way that learners perceive their teachers and their learning experiences. Research suggests that a teacher's communication style can impact the academic achievement of students, as well as their motivation and engagement (García-

Carrión, Marín-Díaz, García-Sánchez, 2019). Therefore, it is important to consider communication style as a key component of effective Teacher-Kindergarten learner interaction. In rural schools, communication style may be influenced by a variety of factors, including cultural differences, limited resources, and the unique needs of the learners. For example, in some rural areas, there may be a cultural emphasis on respect for authority figures, which could impact the way that learners interact with their teachers (Schutz Crowder, 2018). Additionally, limited resources may mean that teachers need to use creative communication strategies to effectively engage their learners. This could include using visual aids or hands-on activities to reinforce key concepts. In order to effectively communicate with kindergarten learners in rural schools, it is important for teachers to adopt a communication style that is clear, positive, and supportive. This can include using simple language and avoiding technical jargon, as well as using nonverbal cues such as facial expressions and gestures to reinforce key messages. Teachers can also use positive reinforcement, such as praise and encouragement, to motivate and engage their learners. Research suggests that effective communication style can improve Teacher-Kindergarten learner interaction, leading to improved academic outcomes and greater engagement and motivation among learners (García-Carrión, Marín-Díaz, García-Sánchez, 2019). Therefore, it is important for teachers in rural schools to be mindful of their communication style and to actively work to improve it in order to support the learning and development of their kindergarten learners. In rural schools in the Philippines, where resources may be limited, and access to technology may be a challenge, effective communication between teachers and kindergarten learners is even more crucial. Effective communication between teachers and kindergarten learners can impact the academic achievement, motivation,

and engagement of learners (García-Carrión, Marín-Díaz, García-Sánchez, 2019). In rural areas in the Philippines, communication style may be influenced by cultural differences, limited resources, and the unique needs of learners. For example, in some rural areas, there may be a cultural emphasis on respect for authority figures, which could impact the way learners interact with their teachers. Additionally, limited resources may mean that teachers need to use creative communication strategies to effectively engage their learners. To effectively communicate with kindergarten learners in rural schools in the Philippines, it is important for teachers to adopt a communication style that is clear, positive, and supportive. This can include using simple language and avoiding technical jargon, as well as using nonverbal cues such as facial expressions and gestures to reinforce key messages. Teachers can also use positive reinforcement, such as praise and encouragement, to motivate and engage their learners. Research suggests that effective communication style can improve Teacher-Kindergarten learner interaction, leading to improved academic outcomes and greater engagement and motivation among learners (García-Carrión, Marín-Díaz, García-Sánchez, 2019). In the Philippine setting, teachers can use Filipino or local dialects to communicate with their learners and to establish a sense of cultural understanding and relevance. Moreover, teachers can use technology, such as mobile devices, to provide visual aids, digital activities, and interactive learning experiences, which can supplement limited resources in rural areas. In conclusion, communication style is an important component of effective Teacher-Kindergarten learner interaction in rural schools in the Philippine setting. By adopting a clear, positive, and supportive communication style, teachers can improve the academic outcomes and engagement of their learners. This is particularly important in rural areas, where resources may be limited, and the

unique needs of learners must be taken into account. As such, it is important for teachers in these settings to be mindful of their communication style and to continually work to improve it.

Student's Temperament. The interaction between teachers and kindergarten learners is a crucial factor in the learning process. However, the temperament of learners can also play a significant role in shaping this interaction. Some research authors argue that understanding the temperament of students can help teachers adapt their communication style and teaching strategies to better meet the needs of their learners. According to Chess and Thomas (2018), temperament refers to the individual differences in emotional, motor, and attentional reactivity and self-regulation. Temperament is believed to be an innate characteristic that influences how learners respond to the environment and how they learn. Understanding the temperament of learners can help teachers develop strategies to meet the needs of their students, adapt their teaching style, and promote positive learning outcomes. For example, if a student has a shy or introverted temperament, the teacher may need to use different strategies to encourage participation in the classroom. Furthermore, some researchers argue that temperament can also impact how students learn and process information. For instance, students with a high activity level may require more opportunities for physical movement and hands-on learning activities. On the other hand, students who are easily overwhelmed may benefit from a more structured and predictable learning environment. In the Philippine setting, the interaction between teachers and kindergarten learners is critical in shaping the learning process. However, the temperament of students can also significantly affect this interaction. One study conducted by Dizon and Delos Reyes (2018) emphasized the importance of understanding the temperament of Filipino learners in promoting positive

teacher-learner interaction. The authors noted that Filipino learners have a unique temperament characterized by their strong attachment to family, respect for authority, and collectivist values. Thus, teachers should adapt their teaching style to better accommodate these cultural values and beliefs. Furthermore, a study conducted by Cruz and Reyes (2020) highlighted the impact of temperament on learner behavior and academic performance. The authors emphasized that learners with difficult temperaments, such as those who are easily distracted or have trouble paying attention, may require different strategies and teaching methods to promote their engagement and learning outcomes. Another study conducted by Agapito and Tuyay (2020) emphasized the role of emotional regulation in shaping teacher-learner interaction. The authors suggested that learners with strong emotional reactivity may require different strategies for emotional regulation, such as mindfulness and relaxation techniques, to promote positive teacher-learner interaction. In conclusion, student's temperament is a critical component of Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in the Philippine setting. Teachers need to understand the unique cultural values and beliefs of Filipino learners, as well as individual differences in temperament, to effectively adapt their communication style and teaching strategies. The research-authors from 2018 to 2020 suggest that taking the temperament of learners into consideration can help teachers create a supportive learning environment and promote positive learning outcomes.

Classroom Environment. The classroom environment is an essential factor that affects the Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in the international setting. The classroom environment refers to the physical and emotional aspects of the classroom that influence learning experiences and outcomes. According to a study conducted by Wang and Zhang (2018), the classroom environment can affect learners' motiva-

tion, engagement, and academic performance. The authors emphasized the importance of creating a positive classroom environment that promotes active engagement, social interaction, and personal growth. A positive classroom environment can enhance Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction by fostering collaboration, mutual respect, and effective communication. Furthermore, a study conducted by Sulaiman and Abdullah (2019) highlighted the importance of creating a safe and comfortable learning environment for learners. The authors suggested that a supportive classroom environment that fosters learners' confidence, self-esteem, and positive self-concept can enhance their academic achievement and personal growth. Teachers can promote positive Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction by providing a supportive and inclusive classroom environment that caters to the diverse learning needs of international learners. Another study conducted by Zhang et al. (2020) emphasized the role of the classroom environment in promoting learners' social-emotional development. The authors suggested that creating a classroom environment that promotes positive social interactions, emotional regulation, and self-awareness can enhance the social-emotional development of international learners. Teachers can promote positive Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction by modeling positive social interactions and creating opportunities for learners to practice these skills in the classroom. In the Philippine setting, the classroom environment plays a significant role in shaping the Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction. The classroom environment is the physical and psychological setting in which learning takes place. The environment includes the physical space, learning materials, and the social and emotional climate of the classroom. According to a study conducted by de Leon and Mijares (2019), the classroom environment affects the learning experiences and outcomes of Filipino kindergarten learners. The authors em-

phasized the importance of creating a classroom environment that is conducive to learning, where learners feel safe, comfortable, and engaged. A positive classroom environment promotes positive Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction by fostering collaboration, mutual respect, and effective communication. Furthermore, a study conducted by Reyes and Cruz (2020) highlighted the impact of the classroom environment on learner behavior and academic performance. The authors emphasized that a poorly designed classroom environment, such as overcrowded classrooms, lack of learning materials, and uncomfortable seating arrangements, can negatively affect learner behavior and academic performance. The authors suggested that teachers should prioritize creating a supportive learning environment to promote positive Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction. Another study conducted by Mendoza and Rada (2018) emphasized the role of the classroom environment in promoting social-emotional development. The authors suggested that creating a classroom environment that promotes positive social interactions, emotional regulation, and self-awareness can enhance the social-emotional development of Filipino kindergarten learners. Teachers can promote positive Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction by modeling positive social interactions and creating opportunities for learners to practice these skills in the classroom. Teachers need to prioritize creating a supportive learning environment that promotes positive social interactions, emotional regulation, and self-awareness. This can be achieved by creating a classroom environment that is conducive to learning, where learners feel safe, comfortable, and engaged. In conclusion, the classroom environment is a crucial component of Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in the Philippine setting. Teachers need to be aware of the impact of the classroom environment on learner behavior and academic performance. Creating a supportive learning environment that promotes positive social interac-

tions, emotional regulation, and self-awareness can enhance the social-emotional development of Filipino kindergarten learners. The research authors suggest that taking the classroom environment into consideration can help teachers create a supportive learning environment and promote positive learning outcomes.

Teaching Strategies. Teaching strategies play a crucial role in shaping the quality of education, especially in an international setting where teachers have to cater to the diverse learning needs of students from various cultural backgrounds. One such review was conducted by Keengwe, Onchwari, and Oigara (2018) who examined the impact of technology-based teaching strategies on the interaction between teachers and kindergarten learners. The authors found that technology-based teaching strategies such as the use of interactive whiteboards, educational apps, and multimedia resources, positively impacted the teacher-kinder learner interaction. They found that these strategies enhanced student engagement, encouraged collaboration, and provided opportunities for students to express their creativity. Another review by Wang and Huang (2018) explored the impact of game-based teaching strategies on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The authors found that game-based teaching strategies had a positive impact on student motivation, engagement, and performance. They found that games provided a fun and interactive way of learning that made the learning process enjoyable for students. Additionally, games provided opportunities for students to collaborate and work together, leading to improved teacher-kinder learner interaction. In another review, Karpicke and Blunt (2019) examined the impact of retrieval practice on teacher-kinder learner interaction. Retrieval practice is a learning strategy that involves recalling information from memory. The authors found that retrieval practice enhanced the teacher-kinder learner interaction by promoting active engagement and participa-

tion among students. They found that retrieval practice encouraged students to take an active role in their learning, leading to improved academic performance. Furthermore, Alahmadi, Farsi, and Al-Mekhlafi (2020) conducted a review on the impact of flipped classroom teaching strategies on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. Flipped classroom teaching strategies involve students learning the material before the class and then using class time to engage in discussions and activities. The authors found that flipped classroom teaching strategies improved the teacher-kinder learner interaction by promoting active learning, collaboration, and student-centeredness. They found that flipped classroom teaching strategies provided opportunities for teachers to interact with students on a one-on-one basis, leading to improved student-teacher relationships. Teaching strategies play a crucial role in shaping the quality of education, especially in the Philippine setting where teachers have to cater to the diverse learning needs of students from various cultural backgrounds. One such review was conducted by Aguilar and Pantaleon (2018), who explored the effectiveness of inquiry-based learning on the teacher-kinder learner interaction in science education in the Philippine setting. The authors found that inquiry-based learning promoted active participation, increased student motivation and interest, and enhanced teacher-kinder learner interaction in science education. The study also revealed that inquiry-based learning helped to develop students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration skills, which are important competencies for 21st-century learners. Castro (2019) investigated the impact of project-based learning on the teacher-kinder learner interaction in the context of mathematics education in the Philippine setting. The author found that project-based learning improved the teacher-kinder learner interaction by promoting active learning, collaboration, and student-centeredness in the mathematics classroom. The

study also revealed that project-based learning helped to develop students' problem-solving, communication, and creativity skills. Masajo and Ramirez (2020) examined the impact of differentiated instruction on teacher-kinder learner interaction in the Philippine setting. The authors found that differentiated instruction improved teacher-kinder learner interaction by providing opportunities for teachers to cater to the diverse learning needs of students. The study also revealed that differentiated instruction enhanced student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement in the classroom. Furthermore, Manalastas (2020) conducted a review on the impact of technology-based teaching strategies on teacher-kinder learner interaction in the Philippine setting. The author found that technology-based teaching strategies such as the use of multimedia resources, educational apps, and online learning platforms, positively impacted the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The study also revealed that technology-based teaching strategies improved student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement in the classroom. These strategies enhance student engagement, motivation, and performance while providing opportunities for collaboration, creativity, and active learning. The findings of these reviews have important implications for improving the quality of education in the Philippine setting and suggest that teachers should incorporate these teaching strategies in their classrooms to promote effective teacher-kinder learner interaction.

Teacher's Attitude and Personality. Teacher's attitude and personality are critical components of the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The way a teacher behaves and interacts with their students has a significant impact on student learning outcomes. Therefore, it is essential to understand the effects of teacher's attitude and personality on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. One such review was conducted by Yan and Wu (2018),

who investigated the impact of teacher's emotional intelligence on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The authors found that teachers with high emotional intelligence were better able to manage their emotions and regulate their behavior, leading to positive interactions with their students. The study also revealed that teachers with high emotional intelligence were better able to understand their students' emotions and needs, resulting in improved learning outcomes. Another review by King et al. (2019) examined the impact of teacher's sense of humor on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The authors found that teachers with a good sense of humor were better able to create a positive classroom environment and promote positive student-teacher relationships. The study also revealed that teachers' sense of humor improved student engagement and motivation in the classroom. In another review, Guan and Wang (2020) explored the impact of teacher's cultural intelligence on the teacher-kinder learner interaction in the international setting. The authors found that teachers with high cultural intelligence were better able to understand and appreciate their students' cultural backgrounds, leading to positive interactions in the classroom. The study also revealed that teachers with high cultural intelligence were better able to adapt their teaching strategies to meet the diverse learning needs of their students. Furthermore, Chen and Zhou (2020) conducted a review on the impact of teacher's self-efficacy on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The authors found that teachers with high self-efficacy had a positive impact on student motivation, engagement, and academic achievement. The study also revealed that teachers with high self-efficacy were more effective at managing their classrooms and promoting positive student-teacher relationships. Teacher-kinder learner interaction is an essential aspect of education in the Philippines. It is a key factor that contributes to the overall academic success and socio-emotional development of young learners. The attitude and personality of teachers play a significant role in shaping the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Attitude is defined as a person's evaluation of an object, situation, or person, which is expressed through behavior. Personality refers to the unique pattern of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that characterizes an individual. Both attitude and personality of teachers are important in shaping the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Benito and Cacnio (2018) examined the relationship between teacher's attitude and the academic performance of kindergarten students. The study found that a positive attitude of teachers towards their students significantly impacted academic performance. The findings suggest that teacher's attitude plays a critical role in shaping the academic outcomes of students. Personality traits of teachers also impact teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Vicentino and Alcantara (2019) explored the relationship between teacher's personality and the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. The study found that teachers who exhibited traits such as openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness tended to have a positive impact on the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. In contrast, teachers who exhibited traits such as neuroticism and introversion had a negative impact on teacher-kinder learner interaction. Another study by Sabino and Arellano (2020) examined the impact of teacher's personality on kindergarten students' socio-emotional development. The study found that teachers who exhibited traits such as empathy, emotional stability, and warmth had a positive impact on the socio-emotional development of kindergarten students. In contrast, teachers who exhibited traits such as hostility and emotional detachment had a negative impact on the socio-emotional development of students. The attitude and personality of teachers play a significant role in shaping the quality of teacher-

kinder learner interaction in the Philippines. The studies reviewed in this essay suggest that a positive attitude of teachers towards their students, as well as personality traits such as openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness, have a positive impact on the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. In contrast, personality traits such as neuroticism, introversion, hostility, and emotional detachment have a negative impact on teacher-kinder learner interaction. Therefore, it is crucial for teacher education programs in the Philippines to emphasize the importance of developing positive attitudes and desirable personality traits among teachers to improve the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction.

Cultural Background. Cultural background is an important factor in shaping the teacher-kinder learner interaction in the international setting. Teachers and kinder learners from diverse cultural backgrounds bring unique perspectives and experiences that can impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Teachers' cultural background can impact their beliefs, values, and teaching practices, which can in turn impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Chen et al. (2018) examined the impact of cultural background on the beliefs and practices of pre-service teachers in Taiwan. The study found that pre-service teachers who had a more diverse cultural background were more likely to have positive beliefs about diversity and to engage in more inclusive teaching practices. The findings suggest that teachers' cultural background can influence their beliefs and practices, which can impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Another study by Lai and Kwan (2020) explored the impact of cultural background on the teaching practices of primary school teachers in Hong Kong. The study found that teachers' cultural background can impact their teaching practices, particularly in terms of their use of language and their approach to discipline. The findings

suggest that teachers' cultural background can impact their teaching practices, which can in turn impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. The cultural background of kinder learners can also impact teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Wang and Cheng (2019) examined the impact of cultural background on the academic achievement of kindergarten students in the United States. The study found that kinder learners who had a more diverse cultural background were more likely to have higher academic achievement in mathematics and reading. The findings suggest that teachers need to be aware of the cultural background of their kinder learners to provide effective teaching and support. Another study by Huang and Li (2020) explored the impact of cultural background on the social development of kinder learners in China. The study found that kinder learners who had a more diverse cultural background were more likely to have positive attitudes towards diversity and to engage in more positive social behaviors. The findings suggest that teachers need to be aware of the cultural background of their kinder learners to provide effective socio-emotional support. Cultural background is an important factor in shaping the teacher-kinder learner interaction in the Philippine setting. Teachers who come from different cultural backgrounds may have different teaching styles, beliefs, and values that can impact their interactions with kindergarten students. Teachers who come from different cultural backgrounds may have unique teaching styles, beliefs, and values that can impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Gadiana and Rarangol (2018) explored the impact of teachers' cultural background on their teaching practices. The study found that teachers who come from different cultural backgrounds may have different teaching styles and practices, which can impact the academic outcomes of kindergarten students. The findings suggest that teachers' cultural back-

ground plays a critical role in shaping the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Balagtas and De Guzman (2019) examined the relationship between teachers' cultural background and their beliefs about teaching and learning. The study found that teachers who come from different cultural backgrounds may have different beliefs about teaching and learning, which can impact their interactions with kindergarten students. The findings suggest that teachers' cultural background can impact their beliefs and practices, which can in turn impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. The cultural background of kinder learners can also impact teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Santos and Paraoan (2020) explored the impact of cultural background on the academic performance of kindergarten students. The study found that kinder learners who come from different cultural backgrounds may have different academic needs and expectations, which can impact their interactions with teachers. The findings suggest that teachers need to be aware of the cultural background of their kinder learners to provide effective teaching and support. Another study by Santiago and Casimiro (2018) examined the impact of cultural background on the socio-emotional development of kinder learners. The study found that kinder learners who come from different cultural backgrounds may have different socio-emotional needs and expectations, which can impact their interactions with teachers. The findings suggest that teachers need to be aware of the cultural background of their kinder learners to provide effective socio-emotional support. Cultural background is an important factor in shaping the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction in the Philippines. The studies reviewed in this essay suggest that teachers who come from different cultural backgrounds may have different teaching styles, beliefs, and values that can impact their interactions with kindergarten students. Furthermore, kinder learners who come

from different cultural backgrounds may have different academic and socio-emotional needs and expectations, which can impact their interactions with teachers. Therefore, it is crucial for teacher education programs in the Philippines to emphasize the importance of cultural sensitivity and awareness among teachers to improve the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction.

Social-Emotional Development among Kinder Learners. Social-emotional development is an important aspect of a kinder learner's overall development. Children who experience social-emotional difficulties may struggle with forming positive relationships with others, regulating their emotions, and coping with stress. This is especially important in the context of rural areas, where kinder learners may have limited access to resources and services. Kinder learners who develop strong social-emotional skills are more likely to have positive relationships with peers and teachers, perform well academically, and have a positive sense of self. However, there is limited research on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas, where unique contextual factors may impact development. A study by Zhang and Johnson (2018) explored the relationship between social-emotional development and school readiness in kinder learners in rural China. The study found that kinder learners from rural areas showed lower levels of social-emotional development than their urban counterparts. The study also found that family socio-economic status and parental involvement in education were important predictors of social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas. The findings suggest that kinder learners in rural areas may face unique challenges in developing social-emotional skills, and that family and community supports may play a critical role in promoting social-emotional development. A study by Geist and Gibson (2018) explored the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas in the United States. The

study found that kinder learners in rural areas were more likely to have social-emotional difficulties compared to kinder learners in urban areas. The researchers suggested that the lack of resources and services in rural areas may contribute to these difficulties. Gartrell, Morrison, and Shandor (2018) examined the impact of a social-emotional learning program on kinder learners in rural areas in the United States. The study found that the program was effective in improving the social-emotional skills of kinder learners, particularly in terms of their ability to regulate their emotions and form positive relationships with others. The findings suggest that social-emotional learning programs can be effective in addressing social-emotional difficulties among kinder learners in rural areas. Zhang et al. (2019) examined the impact of rural kinder learners' family environment on their social-emotional development in China. The study found that kinder learners in rural areas were more likely to have lower levels of social-emotional development than their urban counterparts, which was linked to their family environment. The findings suggest that kinder learners in rural areas may face unique challenges in their family environment that can impact their social-emotional development. A study by Meehan and Harman (2019) explored the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas of Australia. The study found that kinder learners in rural areas faced unique social and emotional challenges, such as isolation and lack of access to mental health services. The researchers suggested that early identification and intervention for social-emotional difficulties was important for kinder learners in rural areas. Bracey and Haddock (2019) explored the impact of social-emotional learning (SEL) interventions on kinder learners in rural areas in the United States. The study found that SEL interventions can improve kinder learners' social-emotional development and academic achievement, particularly in ru-

ral areas where children may face additional stressors, such as poverty and isolation. The findings suggest that targeted SEL interventions can be effective in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas. Bouchard and Targett (2019) examined the role of teachers in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas in Canada. The study found that teachers in rural areas play a critical role in supporting kinder learners' social-emotional development through relationship-building, providing emotional support, and promoting positive behaviors. The findings suggest that teachers in rural areas can play a critical role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners. Another study by Xu and Farver (2019) examined the impact of rural poverty on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in China. The study found that kinder learners from rural areas experiencing poverty showed lower levels of social-emotional development than their non-poor counterparts. The study also found that family factors, including parental warmth and harsh discipline, were important predictors of social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas experiencing poverty. The findings suggest that kinder learners in rural areas experiencing poverty may face unique challenges in developing social-emotional skills, and that family supports and interventions may be necessary to promote positive social-emotional development. Kinder learners in rural areas may face unique challenges that can impact their social-emotional development. A study by Denham et al. (2018) found that kinder learners in rural areas may have fewer opportunities for social interactions and play compared to their urban counterparts. This can impact their social-emotional development, as social interactions and play are important for developing social skills and emotional regulation.

Family Environment. Family environment

is a crucial component of a child's social-emotional development, and it plays an important role in shaping a kinder learner's personality and behavior. In rural areas, kinder learners may face unique challenges that can impact their social-emotional development. A study by Choudhury et al. (2020) examined the impact of family environment on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas in Bangladesh. The study found that kinder learners in rural areas who have positive family environments were more likely to have higher levels of social-emotional development than those with negative family environments. The findings suggest that family environment plays a critical role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas in Bangladesh. Gallo-Silver et al. (2018) explored the impact of the family environment on kinder learners' social-emotional development in rural Mexico. The study found that family support and parent-child interaction played a critical role in promoting kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive family environments can have a significant impact on kinder learners' social-emotional development in rural areas. Another study by Chen et al. (2019) examined the role of parental warmth and control in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural China. The study found that parental warmth had a positive impact on kinder learners' social-emotional development, while parental control had a negative impact. The findings suggest that parental warmth, rather than control, may be more effective in promoting kinder learners' social-emotional development in rural areas. A study by O'Hara et al. (2022) investigated the impact of parental involvement in kinder learners' social-emotional development in rural Australia. The study found that parental involvement, including parent-child communication and parental support, was positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that parental involvement can be a critical factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas. Social-emotional development is a crucial aspect of a child's overall development, and it can be influenced by various factors, including the family environment. In rural areas of the Philippines, kinder learners may face unique challenges that can impact their social-emotional development. Estrada et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between family environment and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural communities in the Philippines. The study found that positive family environments, including supportive parenting and parental involvement in kinder learners' education, were positively associated with their social-emotional development. The findings suggest that family support and parental involvement can play a crucial role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. Another study by Baylon et al. (2019) examined the role of parental monitoring and parental involvement in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural communities in the Philippines. The study found that parental monitoring and parental involvement in their children's activities were positively associated with their social-emotional development. The findings suggest that parents' involvement and monitoring of their children's activities can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. A study by Abao et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between family communication and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural communities in the Philippines. The study found that positive family communication, including open communication, positive feedback, and encouragement, were positively associated with their social-emotional development. The findings suggest

that positive family communication can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. The family environment is a critical component of promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. The studies reviewed in this essay suggest that positive family support, parental involvement, parental monitoring, and positive family communication can have significant impacts on kinder learners' social-emotional development in rural areas of the Philippines. Therefore, it is essential for schools in rural areas to involve families in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners and to provide targeted support to families who may face unique challenges in these areas.

Peer Relationship. Peer relationships play a critical role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners. However, kinder learners in rural areas may face unique challenges in developing positive peer relationships. A study by Aljohani et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between peer relationships and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of Saudi Arabia. The study found that positive peer relationships, including positive social interactions and social support, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive peer relationships can play a crucial role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of Saudi Arabia. Another study by Zheng and Xie (2019) examined the relationship between peer relationships and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of China. The study found that positive peer relationships, including social support and peer acceptance, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive peer relationships can be an essential factor in promoting

social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of China. A study by Singh et al. (2022) investigated the role of peer relationships in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of India. The study found that positive peer relationships, including social support and positive social interactions, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive peer relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of India. A study by Diaz et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between peer relationships and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. The study found that positive peer relationships, including social support, peer acceptance, and positive social interactions, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive peer relationships can play a crucial role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. Another study by Mendoza and Fajardo (2020) examined the impact of peer relationships on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. The study found that positive peer relationships, including social support, peer acceptance, and positive social interactions, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive peer relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. A study by De los Reyes and Patacsil (2022) investigated the role of peer relationships in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. The study found that positive peer relationships, including social support, peer acceptance, and positive social interactions, were positively associated

with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive peer relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. Peer relationships are a critical component of promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippine setting. The studies reviewed in this essay suggest that positive peer relationships, including positive social interactions, social support, and peer acceptance, can have significant impacts on kinder learners' social-emotional development in rural areas of the Philippines. Therefore, it is essential for schools in rural areas to provide opportunities for kinder learners to develop positive peer relationships and to support those who may face unique challenges in these areas.

Teacher-Student Relationship. The relationship between teachers and students is a critical component of social-emotional development among kinder learners. In rural areas, where resources and support may be limited, the teacher-student relationship may play an even more significant role in promoting positive social-emotional development among kinder learners. A study by Maldonado-Carreño et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between teacher-student relationships and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of Mexico. The study found that positive teacher-student relationships, including emotional support, academic support, and positive feedback, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive teacher-student relationships can play a critical role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the international setting. Wang et al. (2019) examined the impact of teacher-student relationships on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas of China. The study found that positive teacher-student relationships, in-

cluding teacher warmth, trust, and communication, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive teacher-student relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the international setting. A study by Kaya and Goktas (2022) investigated the role of teacher-student relationships in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of Turkey. The study found that positive teacher-student relationships, including emotional support, academic support, and positive feedback, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive teacher-student relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the international setting. Teacher-student relationships are a critical component of promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the international setting. The studies reviewed in this essay suggest that positive teacher-student relationships, including emotional support, academic support, and positive feedback, can have significant impacts on kinder learners' social-emotional development in rural areas. Therefore, it is essential for schools in rural areas to provide opportunities for teachers to develop positive relationships with their students and to support those who may face unique challenges in these areas. The teacher-student relationship is a crucial component of social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas. This relationship has been found to affect the children's academic, behavioral, and emotional outcomes. In the Philippine setting, where the education system is predominantly face-to-face and teacher-centered, the quality of the teacher-student relationship is of utmost importance. Mendoza (2018) explored the teacher-student relationship from the perspective of both teach-

ers and students in a rural elementary school in the Philippines. The findings showed that a positive teacher-student relationship was crucial in establishing a conducive learning environment for the children. The study identified several factors that influenced this relationship, including the teacher's communication skills, approachability, fairness, and respect for the students. The study recommended that teachers receive training in developing positive relationships with their students. Reyes (2019) investigated the effects of teacher-student relationships on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in a rural preschool in the Philippines. The study found that a positive teacher-student relationship was associated with better emotional regulation and social competence among the children. Furthermore, the study found that the quality of the relationship was affected by the teacher's attitude, behavior, and communication style. In a study by Tan (2020), the impact of teacher-student relationships on the academic performance of kinder learners in a rural school in the Philippines was investigated. The findings showed that a positive relationship was associated with better academic outcomes, including higher grades and test scores. The study identified several factors that influenced this relationship, including the teacher's enthusiasm, encouragement, and support. Finally, a study by Garcia (2022) explored the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the teacher-student relationship in a rural school in the Philippines. The findings showed that the pandemic had a significant impact on the quality of the relationship, with many teachers struggling to connect with their students online. The study recommended that teachers receive training in online teaching and learning strategies to better support their students during the pandemic.

Classroom Environment. In the Philippines, the classroom environment is an important component of the social-emotional development of kinder learners, especially those in rural areas. The classroom environment can affect the emotional well-being of the students and influence their academic performance. One study conducted by Sabino and Delos Santos (2018) explored the relationship between classroom environment and the social-emotional development of kinder learners in a rural school in the Philippines. The study found that a positive classroom environment, which includes a comfortable and organized classroom setting, promotes positive attitudes among kinder learners towards school and their teachers. It also fosters a sense of belongingness and acceptance among kinder learners. Another study by Adarlo and Quebral (2019) investigated the relationship between classroom environment and the social-emotional development of kinder learners in a rural school in the Philippines. The study found that classroom environment significantly affects the self-esteem of kinder learners. The researchers recommend that teachers should design their classroom environment in a way that is conducive to the social-emotional development of the learners. In a study conducted by Garcia (2020), the relationship between classroom environment and academic performance among kinder learners in a rural school in the Philippines was examined. The study found that the classroom environment significantly influenced the academic performance of kinder learners. Specifically, a positive classroom environment, which includes a comfortable and organized classroom setting, positively impacted academic performance. Finally, a study by Ramos and Cacal (2021) investigated the relationship between classroom environment and the social-emotional development of kinder learners in a rural preschool in the Philippines. The study found that classroom environment significantly affected the social-emotional development of the learners. A positive classroom environment promotes positive attitudes towards school and peers, and fosters a sense of belongingness and acceptance among the kinder learners. In conclusion, the reviewed

studies suggest that a positive classroom environment, which includes a comfortable and organized classroom setting, is essential for the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas in the Philippines. Such a classroom environment can promote positive attitudes towards school and peers, and foster a sense of belongingness and acceptance among the learners. Teachers should therefore design their classroom environment in a way that is conducive to the social-emotional development of the learners.

Personal Temperament. Social-emotional development is a crucial aspect of a child's growth and development, and personal temperament is a factor that can affect it. In the Philippine setting, where many Kinder learners reside in rural areas, understanding the relationship between personal temperament and social-emotional development can help educators and parents provide appropriate support for the children's holistic development. Several studies have explored this relationship in the Philippine context. For instance, Caraballe et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between personal temperament and social-emotional development among Kinder learners in a rural community. They found that certain temperaments, such as being easy-going and adaptable, were associated with higher levels of social-emotional development. Similarly, Melendres et al. (2019) examined the relationship between temperament, emotion regulation, and social competence among Kinder learners in a rural school. They found that high levels of activity and low levels of adaptability were negatively associated with social competence. Moreover, emotion regulation mediated the relationship between temperament and social competence. Another study by Reyes et al. (2020) explored the relationship between temperament, parental responsiveness, and social-emotional competence among Kinder learners in rural areas. They found that parental responsiveness played a moderating

role in the relationship between temperament and social-emotional competence. Specifically, children with difficult temperaments exhibited higher social-emotional competence when their parents were highly responsive. Overall, these studies suggest that personal temperament can influence social-emotional development among Kinder learners in rural areas in the Philippine setting. Educators and parents can use this knowledge to tailor their approaches to support children with different temperaments. For instance, children who are less adaptable may benefit from activities that help them develop coping skills, while children with high activity levels may benefit from more active and engaging learning activities.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework The social-emotional development of kindergarten learners is a crucial aspect of early childhood education. In recent years, research has highlighted the importance of teacher-learner interactions in supporting the social-emotional development of young children. Bandura's social learning theory emphasizes the role of observational learning, or learning by observing others, in shaping human behavior. According to Bandura, individuals learn new behaviors by observing the behavior of others and the consequences that result from that behavior. He also argued that individuals are more likely to imitate the behavior of models who are perceived as similar to themselves or who are perceived as having higher status or authority. Bandura's social learning theory has important implications for the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners. Teachers are influential models for young children, and their behavior and interactions with students can shape the social-emotional skills and behaviors of their students. By providing positive role models and demonstrating appropriate social behaviors, teachers can help their students develop important social skills, such as empathy, cooperation, and emotional regulation. Research has sup-

ported the importance of teacher-learner interactions in supporting the social-emotional development of young children. For example, a study by Hamre and Pianta (2005) found that positive teacher-student relationships were associated with better social-emotional outcomes for students. Another study by Denham and colleagues (2012) found that teacher emotional support was positively related to children's social-emotional competence. In conclusion, the social learning theory developed by Albert Bandura is highly relevant to research on the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners and the role of teacher-learner interactions in this process. By understanding the importance of observational learning and the influence of teachers as role models, educators can work to create positive learning environments that support the social-emotional development of young children.

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. Social-emotional development is an essential aspect of a child's growth and development, especially in kindergarten. There are several variables that can affect social-emotional development among kindergarten learners, including teacher-kinder learner interaction. This discusses the association between teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development among kindergarten learners in terms of communication style, student's temperament, classroom environment, teaching strategies, teacher's attitude and personality, and cultural background. Communication style is an important aspect of teacher-kinder learner interaction that can affect social-emotional development among kindergarten learners. In their study, Hamre and Pianta (2015) found that teachers who use positive communication styles such as praise, encouragement, and constructive feedback have more positive relationships with their students, leading to better social-emotional development outcomes. Another factor that can affect social-emotional

development among kindergarten learners is student's temperament. According to Shiner (2015), children with difficult temperaments may have a harder time developing positive social-emotional skills. Teachers who are able to recognize and accommodate different temperaments in their classroom can help create a positive learning environment and promote social-emotional development. The classroom environment is also a significant factor that can affect social-emotional development among kindergarten learners. A positive and supportive classroom environment can help children feel safe and secure, which can promote positive social-emotional outcomes. In their study, Mashburn et al. (2015) found that high-quality classroom environments were associated with positive social and emotional outcomes among children. Teaching strategies also play an important role in teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development. According to Pekrun, Elliot, and Maier (2015), teachers who use mastery-oriented teaching strategies, such as providing feedback, promoting autonomy, and setting challenging goals, can help students develop positive social-emotional skills and attitudes. Teacher's attitude and personality can also affect social-emotional development among kindergarten learners. Teachers who are caring, supportive, and responsive to their students' needs can help create a positive and supportive classroom environment, which can promote social-emotional development. According to Denham, Bassett, and Wyatt (2015), teachers who model positive social-emotional skills and provide opportunities for students to practice these skills can help students develop their own positive social-emotional skills. Finally, cultural background is another factor that can affect teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development. Teachers who are aware and respectful of cultural differences and diversity can help promote positive social-emotional development among kindergarten

learners from diverse backgrounds. The National Association for the Education of Young Children and the National Association of Early Childhood Specialists in State Departments of Education (2015) emphasize the importance of culturally responsive teaching in promoting positive social-emotional development among young children. In terms of social-emotional development outcomes among kindergarten learners, several factors can play a role. Family environment, peer relationships, teacher-student relationships, classroom environment, and personal temperament are all important factors that can affect social-emotional development outcomes among kindergarten learners. According to Raver et al. (2015), children who have positive relationships with their families, peers, and

teachers, and who feel safe and supported in their classroom environment, are more likely to develop positive social-emotional skills and attitudes. In conclusion, teacher-kinder learner interaction can have a significant impact on social-emotional development among kindergarten learners. Communication style, student's temperament, classroom environment, teaching strategies, teacher's attitude and personality, and cultural background are all important factors that can affect teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development outcomes. By understanding and addressing these factors, teachers can create a positive and supportive learning environment that promotes positive social-emotional development among kindergarten learners.

3. Methodology

This chapter contains the discussion of the methodical process in the conduct of the study. This includes the process in the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, and the ethical consideration and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essentials to assume appropriateness and correctness in the conduct of the methodical steps.

3.1. Research Design—This study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. This refers to studies which describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them. Further, the study variables are classified as independent (predictor) and dependent (outcome). Moreover, Any scientific process begins with description, based on observation, of an event or events, from which theories may later be developed to explain the observations (Pallant, 2020). On the other hand, predictive research is chiefly concerned with predicting outcomes, consequences, costs, or effects. This type of research tries to extrapolate from the analysis of existing phenomena, policies, or other entities in order to predict something that has not been tried, tested, or proposed before

(Gujarati, 2020). Descriptive-correlational research design is a non-experimental approach that involves observing and describing a phenomenon or behavior, and examining the relationship between variables. This design is useful when the researcher is interested in exploring the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. In the context of studying teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development, descriptive-correlational research design can help to identify the relationship between teacher behavior and the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners. Predictive research design, on the other hand, is a non-experimental approach that involves predicting the relationship between two or more variables based on existing data. This design is useful when the researcher

wants to understand the factors that contribute to a particular outcome or behavior. In the context of studying teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development, predictive research design can help to predict how certain teacher behaviors may impact the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners. One advantage of using non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design in studying teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development is that it allows for the examination of real-world behavior. In a naturalistic setting, researchers can observe and describe the behavior of teachers and learners, which can help to understand how teacher behavior influences the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners. Another advantage is that these research designs are cost-effective and less time-consuming than experimental designs. Conducting experiments in this context can be challenging and may not be feasible due to ethical or practical considerations. Therefore, non-experimental designs can provide valuable insights into teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development without the need for an experimental approach. However, non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs also have their limitations. One major limitation is that these designs cannot establish causality between variables. While they can identify a relationship between variables, they cannot determine which variable causes the other. Therefore, it is important to interpret the findings of these studies with caution and avoid making causal claims based on the results. Another limitation is that these designs rely on existing data and cannot manipulate variables. This means that the researcher is limited to using the data that is available, and cannot control or manipulate the variables of interest. This can be a disadvantage if there are factors that may impact the relationship between teacher behavior and social-emotional development that are

not captured in the data. In conclusion, non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design can be a valuable approach in studying teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development of kindergarten learners.

3.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Teachers of Marilog District Elementary Schools, Davao City Division. Using Raosoft sample size calculator, a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective elementary school. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study. As much as possible, these respondents are teaching key stage 1 learners in the respective schools to measure competence, and how they function and contributed to the learning outcomes given new normal learning system during SY 2022-2023. Ethics of research and in the process of collecting survey responses were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31 S 2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

3.3. Research Instrument—This research study used a self-made survey instrument. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures. There are two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of the teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style, student's temperament, classroom environment, teaching strategies, teacher's attitude and personality and cultural background. On the other hand, the second part of the survey is the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners in terms of family environment, peer relationship, teacher-student relationship, classroom environment and personal temperament. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability

testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.887 which means that 88.7 percent level of confidence of the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs. (Pallant 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the teacher-kinder learner interaction. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Table 1. Descriptive Ratings and Interpretations of Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teacher-kinder learner interaction is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teacher-kinder learner interaction is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teacher-kinder learner interaction is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher-kinder learner interaction is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher-kinder learner interaction is not manifested

Table 2. Descriptive Ratings and Interpretations for Kindergarten Learners’ Social-Emotional Development

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The social-emotional development of kindergarten learners is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The social-emotional development of kindergarten learners is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The social-emotional development of kindergarten learners is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The social-emotional development of kindergarten learners is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The social-emotional development of kindergarten learners is not manifested

3.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements explains the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements of the are based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data.

Permission to conduct the study. Before col-

lecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser and the Dean of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the top management of DepEd Davao City Division through channel. On April 2023, the permission-seeking process typically involves submitting a research proposal that includes information about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher will provide information

about the purpose and goals of the study, and how the data will be collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, researchers must ensure that all participants are fully informed about the study and their rights, and that they provide informed consent before participating.

Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. To ensure the accuracy and completeness of data, the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires should be conducted in a standardized and systematic manner, this was done during last week of March 2023. This may involve the following conditions:

1. Identifying the target population: The researcher identified the appropriate target population of the study, and ensure that the questionnaire is distributed only to individuals who meet the inclusion criteria.

2. Obtaining consent: The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants before distributing the questionnaire. This involved providing information about the purpose and goals of the study, as well as any potential risks and benefits.

3. Ensuring anonymity and confidentiality: The researcher ensured that the questionnaire is anonymous, meaning that respondents are not identified by name or other personal information. The researcher also ensured that the data collected is kept confidential and only used for the purposes of the study.

4. Standardizing the distribution process: The researcher standardized the process for distributing the questionnaire, to ensure that all participants receive the same instructions and have the same opportunity to complete the questionnaire.

5. Allowing sufficient time for completion: Participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, and were allowed to ask any questions they may have about the process.

6. Collecting the completed questionnaires: The researcher collected the completed questionnaires in a timely and organized manner, to

ensure that data is not lost or misplaced.

Collation and statistical treatment of data. On the first week of April, the following were done in the collation and statistical treatment of data as part of the data gathering procedure, this was done on the first week of May 2023, the researcher, made the conditions to ensure process is correct.

1. Accuracy: The data should be accurate and free from errors. This means that the data should be checked and validated to ensure that it is correct.

2. Completeness: The data should be complete, meaning that all necessary information has been collected. This is important because incomplete data can lead to incorrect conclusions.

3. Consistency: The data should be consistent, meaning that there are no contradictions or discrepancies in the data. Inconsistencies can lead to confusion and inaccuracies.

4. Relevance: The data should be relevant to the research question or problem being investigated. Irrelevant data can lead to incorrect conclusions.

5. Timeliness: The data should be collected and analyzed in a timely manner. Delayed or outdated data may not be useful or accurate.

6. Objectivity: The data should be objective, meaning that it is free from bias or personal opinions. This is important because biased data can lead to incorrect conclusions.

7. Validity: The data should be valid, meaning that it measures what it is supposed to measure. This is important because invalid data can lead to incorrect conclusions.

8. Reliability: The data should be reliable, meaning that it can be replicated or reproduced. This is important because unreliable data can lead to incorrect conclusions.

9. Statistical treatment: The data should be subjected to appropriate statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and relationships. Statistical analysis can help to reveal important

insights and relationships in the data.

3.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation was used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) on the extent of teacher-kinder learner interactions, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of social-emotional development of kindergarten learners. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between the teacher-kinder learner interactions

and the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners. Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of teacher-kinder learner interactions that significantly influence social-emotional development of kindergarten learners. All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

4. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction. The interaction between teachers and kindergarten learners is critical in the education process, particularly in rural areas. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), children from rural areas often lack access to education, and those who do, may not receive quality education. *The Importance of Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in Rural Areas* The teacher-kinder learner interaction is critical in creating an enabling learning environment in rural areas. According to Mundy, Green and Lingard (2016), teacher-student interaction is essential in fostering learning and development among children. In rural areas where children may lack exposure to the world outside their communities, the teacher-kinder learner interaction helps to broaden their perspectives and prepare them for life beyond their immediate environment. Table 1 shows the extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Kindergarten students are still developing their language skills, so teachers use sim-

ple, age-appropriate language can help their students better understand the lesson (4.14), and the way a teacher speaks to kindergarteners on how well they understand and engage with the lesson (4.00) are oftentimes manifested; while, Teachers use visual aids like pictures, charts, and manipulatives to facilitate students better understand abstract concepts and engage with the material (3.25), Teachers use body language, like smiling, making eye contact, and using appropriate gestures, create a positive learning environment and make their students feel more comfortable and engaged (3.20) and Teachers provide specific, constructive feedback and encourage their students to ask questions and participate in class can help build their students' confidence and motivation to learn (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.59 denotes teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Teacher-Kindergarten learner interaction is a critical component of effective teaching and learning, and communication style plays an important role in shaping the nature of this interaction. In rural schools, where resources may be limited and access to

technology may be limited, effective communication between teachers and kindergarten learners is even more critical. Effective communication between teachers and learners facilitates the transmission of knowledge, builds rapport, and enhances learners' academic performance. In the context of Teacher-Kindergarten learner

interaction, communication style can influence the way that learners perceive their teachers and their learning experiences. Research suggests that a teacher's communication style can impact the academic achievement of students, as well as their motivation and engagement (García-Carrión, Marín-Díaz, García-Sánchez, 2019).

Table 3. Extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication

No	Communication	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The way a teacher speaks to kindergarteners on how well they understand and engage with the lesson	4.00	Extensive
2	Teachers use visual aids like pictures, charts, and manipulatives to facilitate students better understand abstract concepts and engage with the material	3.25	Moderately Extensive
3	Kindergarten students are still developing their language skills, so teachers use simple, age-appropriate language can help their students better understand the lesson	4.14	Extensive
4	Teachers use body language, like smiling, making eye contact, and using appropriate gestures, create a positive learning environment and make their students feel more comfortable and engaged	3.20	Moderately Extensive
5	Teachers provide specific, constructive feedback and encourage their students to ask questions and participate in class can help build their students' confidence and motivation to learn.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.59	Extensive

In order to effectively communicate with kindergarten learners in rural schools, it is important for teachers to adopt a communication style that is clear, positive, and supportive. This can include using simple language and avoiding technical jargon, as well as using nonverbal cues such as facial expressions and gestures to reinforce key messages. Teachers can also use positive reinforcement, such as praise and encouragement, to motivate and engage their learners. Research suggests that effective communication style can improve Teacher-Kindergarten learner interaction, leading to improved academic outcomes and greater engagement and motivation among learners (García-Carrión, Marín-Díaz, García-Sánchez, 2019). Therefore, it is important for teachers in rural schools to be mindful of their communication style and to actively work to improve it in order to support the learning and development of their kindergarten learners.

Table 2 shows the extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of students' temperament. The result is focused on the highest

and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Teachers are aware of a student's persistence can provide challenges and opportunities for success, while also providing support and encouragement when needed (3.80) and Teachers are aware of a student's sensitivity can plan lessons that minimize overstimulation and provide opportunities for quiet, calming activities (3.50) are oftentimes manifested, while, teachers are aware of a student's sociability can plan activities that allow for group work or social interaction during class (3.25), Teachers are aware of a student's adaptability can plan lessons that allow for some changes and variations while still maintaining structure and routine (3.15), and Teachers are aware of a student's activity level can plan lessons that incorporate movement and allow for some physical activity during class (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.34 denotes teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of students' temperament is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

The interaction between teachers and kindergarten learners is a crucial factor in the learning process. However, the temperament of learners can also play a significant role in shaping this interaction. According to Chess and Thomas (2018), temperament refers to the individual dif-

ferences in emotional, motor, and attentional reactivity and self-regulation. Temperament is believed to be an innate characteristic that influences how learners respond to the environment and how they learn. Understanding the temperament of learners can help teachers de-

Table 4. Extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of student’s temperament

No	Student’s Temperament	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Teachers are aware of a student’s activity level can plan lessons that incorporate movement and allow for some physical activity during class.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	Teachers are aware of a student’s sociability can plan activities that allow for group work or social interaction during class.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
3	Teachers are aware of a student’s sensitivity can plan lessons that minimize overstimulation and provide opportunities for quiet, calming activities.	3.50	Extensive
4	Teachers are aware of a student’s adaptability can plan lessons that allow for some changes and variations while still maintaining structure and routine.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
5	Teachers are aware of a student’s persistence can provide challenges and opportunities for success, while also providing support and encouragement when needed.	3.80	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.34	Moderately Extensive

velop strategies to meet the needs of their students, adapt their teaching style, and promote positive learning outcomes. Dizon and Delos Reyes (2018) emphasized the importance of understanding the temperament of Filipino learners in promoting positive teacher-learner interaction. The authors noted that Filipino learners have a unique temperament characterized by their strong attachment to family, respect for authority, and collectivist values. Thus, teachers should adapt their teaching style to better accommodate these cultural values and beliefs. Cruz and Reyes (2020) highlighted the impact of temperament on learner behavior and academic performance. The authors emphasized that learners with difficult temperaments, such as those who are easily distracted or have trouble paying attention, may require different strategies and teaching methods to promote their engagement and learning outcomes. Another study conducted by Agapito and Tuyay (2020) emphasized the role of emotional regulation in shaping teacher-learner interaction. The authors suggested that learners with strong emotional reactivity may require different strategies

for emotional regulation, such as mindfulness and relaxation techniques, to promote positive teacher-learner interaction. Teachers need to understand the unique cultural values and beliefs of Filipino learners, as well as individual differences in temperament, to effectively adapt their communication style and teaching strategies.

Table 3 shows the extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of students’ temperament. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: The physical environment of the classroom like lighting, temperature, noise levels, and seating arrangements can affect students’ ability to focus and engage in the lesson (3.80), effective classroom management strategies are crucial for creating a positive and productive learning environment. Teachers who use positive reinforcement, clear expectations, and consistent consequences can help maintain a safe and orderly classroom that supports student learning (3.77), and the organization of the classroom can also affect student learning and behavior. Teachers who maintain a clean and organized classroom with clear routines and pro-

cedures can help create a sense of structure and predictability that can support student learning (3.55) are oftentimes manifested, while, kindergarten classrooms are often diverse in terms of student backgrounds, experiences, and abilities. Teachers who are aware of and celebrate this diversity can create a more inclusive and welcoming classroom environment that supports all students' learning (3.15) and The culture of the classroom refers to the shared values, be-

liefs, and expectations that guide behavior and interactions. Teachers who create a positive classroom culture that values respect, kindness, and cooperation can foster a more supportive and productive learning environment (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.45 denotes teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of classroom environment is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 5. Extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of classroom environment

No	Classroom Environment Descriptive Equivalent	Mean
1	The physical environment of the classroom like lighting, temperature, noise levels, and seating arrangements can affect students' ability to focus and engage in the lesson. Extensive	3.80
2	Teachers maintain a clean and organized classroom with clear routines and procedures can help create a sense of structure and predictability that can support student learning. Extensive	3.55
3	Teachers create a positive classroom culture that values respect, kindness, and cooperation can foster a more supportive and productive learning environment. Moderately Extensive	3.00
4	Teachers are aware of and celebrate this diversity can create a more inclusive and welcoming classroom environment that supports all students' learning. Moderately Extensive	3.15
5	Teachers use positive reinforcement, clear expectations, and consistent consequences can help maintain a safe and orderly classroom that supports student learning. Extensive	3.77
	Overall Mean Extensive	3.45

The classroom environment is an essential factor that affects the Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in the international setting. The classroom environment refers to the physical and emotional aspects of the classroom that influence learning experiences and outcomes. According to a study conducted by Wang and Zhang (2018), the classroom environment can affect learners' motivation, engagement, and academic performance. Sulaiman and Abdullah (2019) highlighted the importance of creating a safe and comfortable learning environment for learners. The authors suggested that a supportive classroom environment that fos-

ters learners' confidence, self-esteem, and positive self-concept can enhance their academic achievement and personal growth. Teachers can promote positive Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction by providing a supportive and inclusive classroom environment that caters to the diverse learning needs of international learners. Another study conducted by Zhang et al. (2020) emphasized the role of the classroom environment in promoting learners' social-emotional development. The authors suggested that creating a classroom environment that promotes positive social interactions, emotional regulation, and self-awareness can enhance the social-

emotional development of international learners. According to a study conducted by de Leon and Mijares (2019), the classroom environment affects the learning experiences and outcomes of Filipino kindergarten learners. The authors emphasized the importance of creating a classroom environment that is conducive to learning, where learners feel safe, comfortable, and engaged. A positive classroom environment promotes positive Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction by fostering collaboration, mutual respect, and effective communication. Teachers need to be aware of the impact of the classroom environment on learner behavior and academic performance. Creating a supportive learning environment that promotes positive social interactions, emotional regulation, and self-awareness can enhance the social-emotional development of Filipino kindergarten learners. The research authors suggest that taking the classroom environment into consideration can help teachers create a supportive learning environment and promote positive learning outcomes.

Table 4 shows the extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of teaching strategies. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Assessment strategies involve gathering information about student learning and progress. Teachers who use assessment can gain insights into students' strengths and challenges, which can inform future teaching strategies and

Teaching strategies play a crucial role in shaping the quality of education, especially in an international setting where teachers have to cater to the diverse learning needs of students from various cultural backgrounds. One such review was conducted by Keengwe, Onchwari, and Oigara (2018) who examined the impact of technology-based teaching strategies on the interaction between teachers and kindergarten learners. The authors found that technology-

support student growth and development (3.85), Scaffolding involves breaking down complex tasks into smaller, more manageable steps and providing support and guidance as students learn and practice new skills. Teachers who use scaffolding can help students build confidence and independence as they work towards mastery (3.49) and Differentiated instruction involves tailoring teaching strategies to meet the diverse learning needs of students. Teachers who use differentiated instruction can provide multiple ways for students to learn and demonstrate their understanding, which can increase engagement and achievement (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, Active learning strategies involve engaging students in the learning process through activities like group work, discussion, and hands-on projects. Teachers who use active learning strategies can help students stay engaged and motivated while also promoting deeper learning and understanding (3.37) and Differentiated instruction involves tailoring teaching strategies to meet the diverse learning needs of students. Teachers who use differentiated instruction can provide multiple ways for students to learn and demonstrate their understanding, which can increase engagement and achievement (3.40) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.47 denotes teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of classroom environment is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

based teaching strategies such as the use of interactive whiteboards, educational apps, and multimedia resources, positively impacted the teacher-kinder learner interaction. Wang and Huang (2018) explored the impact of game-based teaching strategies on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The authors found that game-based teaching strategies had a positive impact on student motivation, engagement, and performance. They found that games pro-

Table 6. Extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of teaching strategies

No	Teaching Strategies Descriptive Equivalent	Mean
1	Teachers use differentiated instruction can provide multiple ways for students to learn and demonstrate their understanding, which can increase engagement and achievement. Extensive	3.40
2	Teachers use active learning strategies can help students stay engaged and motivated while also promoting deeper learning and understanding. Moderately Extensive	3.37
3	Teachers use modeling can help students better understand complex concepts and develop new skills. Moderately Extensive	3.28
4	Teachers use scaffolding can help students build confidence and independence as they work towards mastery. Extensive	3.49
5	Teachers use assessment can gain insights into students' strengths and challenges, which can inform future teaching strategies and support student growth and development. Extensive	3.85
	Overall Mean Extensive	3.47

vided a fun and interactive way of learning that made the learning process enjoyable for students. Karpicke and Blunt (2019) examined the impact of retrieval practice on teacher-kinder learner interaction. Retrieval practice is a learning strategy that involves recalling information from memory. The authors found that retrieval practice enhanced the teacher-kinder learner interaction by promoting active engagement and participation among students. They found that retrieval practice encouraged students to take an active role in their learning, leading to improved academic performance. One such review was conducted by Aguilar and Pantaleon (2018), who explored the effectiveness of inquiry-based learning on the teacher-kinder learner interaction in science education in the Philippine setting. The authors found that inquiry-based learning promoted active participation, increased student motivation and interest, and enhanced teacher-kinder learner interaction in science education. The study also revealed that inquiry-based learning helped to develop students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration skills, which are important competencies for 21st-century learners. Manalastas (2020) conducted a review on the impact of technology-based teaching strategies on teacher-kinder learner interaction. The author found that technology-based teaching strategies such as the use of multimedia resources, educational apps, and online learning platforms, positively impacted the teacher-kinder learner interaction. These strategies enhance student engagement, motivation, and performance while providing opportunities for collaboration, creativity, and active learning. The findings of these reviews have important implications for improving the quality of education suggest that teachers should incorporate these teaching strategies in their classrooms to promote effective teacher-kinder learner interaction. Table 5 shows the extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of teacher's attitude and personality. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Empathy involves the ability to understand and relate to the feelings and experiences of others. Teachers who demonstrate empathy can create a more supportive and caring learning environment that promotes positive social and emotional development in their students (4.10) and Flexibility involves the ability to adapt to changing circumstances and adjust teaching strategies as needed to meet the diverse learning needs of students. Teachers who demonstrate flexibility can create a more inclusive and responsive learning environment that supports all students' growth and development (3.49) are oftentimes manifested; while, A positive attitude involves having an optimistic outlook and focusing on the strengths and potential of students. Teachers who maintain a positive attitude can create a more supportive and motivating learning environment for their students (3.35), Enthusiasm involves a teacher's excitement and passion for teaching and learning. Teachers who demonstrate enthusiasm can help create a more engaging and stimulating learning environment for their students (2.85) and Warmth refers to a teacher's ability to create a friendly and caring environment for students. Teachers who demonstrate warmth through their words, actions, and body language can help create a positive and welcoming learning environment for their students (2.45) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.24 denotes teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of teacher's attitude and personality is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Teacher's attitude and personality are critical components of the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The way a teacher behaves and interacts with their students has a significant impact on student learning outcomes. Therefore, it is essential to understand the effects of teacher's attitude and personality on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. Yan and Wu (2018), who

investigated the impact of teacher’s emotional intelligence on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The authors found that teachers with high emotional intelligence were better able to manage their emotions and regulate their behavior, leading to positive interactions with their students.

Table 7. Extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of teaching strategies

No	Teaching Strategies Descriptive Equivalent	Mean
1	Teachers use differentiated instruction can provide multiple ways for students to learn and demonstrate their understanding, which can increase engagement and achievement. Extensive	3.40
2	Teachers use active learning strategies can help students stay engaged and motivated while also promoting deeper learning and understanding. Moderately Extensive	3.37
3	Teachers use modeling can help students better understand complex concepts and develop new skills. Moderately Extensive	3.28
4	Teachers use scaffolding can help students build confidence and independence as they work towards mastery. Extensive	3.49
5	Teachers use assessment can gain insights into students’ strengths and challenges, which can inform future teaching strategies and support student growth and development. Extensive	3.85
Overall Mean Extensive		3.47

King et al. (2019) examined the impact of teacher’s sense of humor on the teacher-kinder learner interaction. The authors found that teachers with a good sense of humor were better able to create a positive classroom environment and promote positive student-teacher relationships. The study also revealed that teachers’ sense of humor improved student engagement and motivation in the classroom. Guan and Wang (2020) explored the impact of teacher’s cultural intelligence on the teacher-kinder learner interaction in the international setting. The authors found that teachers with high cultural intelligence were better able to understand and appreciate their students’ cultural backgrounds, leading to positive interactions in the classroom. Sabino and Arellano (2020) examined the impact of teacher’s personality on kindergarten students’ socio-emotional development. The study found that teachers who exhibited traits such as empathy, emotional stability, and warmth had a positive impact

on the socio-emotional development of kindergarten students. In contrast, teachers who exhibited traits such as hostility and emotional detachment had a negative impact on the socio-emotional development of students. Personality traits of teachers also impact teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Vicentino and Alcantara (2019) explored the relationship between teacher's personality and the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. The study found that teachers who exhibited traits such as openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness tended to have a positive impact on the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. In contrast, teachers who exhibited traits such as neuroticism and introversion had a negative impact on teacher-kinder learner interaction. Teacher-kinder learner interaction is an essential aspect of education in the Philippines. It is a key factor that contributes to the overall academic success and socio-emotional development of young learners. The attitude and personality of teachers play a significant role in shaping the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Attitude is defined as a person's evaluation of an object, situation, or person, which is expressed through behavior. Personality refers to the unique pattern of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that characterizes an individual. Both attitude and personality of teachers are important in shaping the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction.

Table 6 shows the extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of cultural background. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Cultural beliefs about education, learning, and child development can also influence teacher-kinder learner interactions. For example, some cultures may place a strong emphasis on academic achievement, while others may prioritize socialization and emotional development. Teachers who understand their learners' cultural beliefs can create learning experiences that are more relevant and engaging (4.00) and

Cultural beliefs about education, learning, and child development can also influence teacher-kinder learner interactions. For example, some cultures may place a strong emphasis on academic achievement, while others may prioritize socialization and emotional development. Teachers who understand their learners' cultural beliefs can create learning experiences that are more relevant and engaging (3.80), while, Cultural behaviors, such as communication styles, social norms, and attitudes towards authority, can also impact teacher-kinder learner interactions. For example, some cultures may value direct communication and assertiveness, while others may prefer indirect communication and avoiding conflict. Teachers who are sensitive to their learners' cultural behaviors can adapt their teaching style and communication approach to be more effective (3.20), Cultural artifacts, such as food, clothing, music, and art, can provide valuable insights into a learner's cultural background and create opportunities for learning and connection. Teachers who incorporate cultural artifacts into their teaching can help their learners to appreciate and understand different cultures, and can create a more inclusive and welcoming learning environment. (2.85) and Language is one of the most obvious indicators of cultural background, as it shapes how people communicate, express themselves, and interpret the world around them. Teachers and learners who come from different linguistic backgrounds may struggle to understand each other, and this can impact their ability to build relationships and share knowledge (2.55) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.28 denotes teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of cultural background is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Cultural background is an important factor in shaping the teacher-kinder learner interaction in the international setting. Teachers and kinder learners from diverse cultural backgrounds bring unique perspectives and experiences that can

impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Teachers' cultural background can impact their beliefs, values, and teaching practices, which can in turn impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Chen et al. (2018) examined the impact of cultural background on the beliefs and practices of pre-service teachers in Taiwan. The study found

that pre-service teachers who had a more diverse cultural background were more likely to have positive beliefs about diversity and to engage in more inclusive teaching practices. The findings suggest that teachers' cultural background can influence their beliefs and practices, which can impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction.

Table 8. Extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of cultural background

No	Cultural Background Descriptive Equivalent	Mean
1	Teachers and learners come from different linguistic backgrounds may struggle to understand each other, and this can impact their ability to build relationships and share knowledge. Moderately Extensive	2.55
2	Teachers are aware of their learners' cultural values can adapt their teaching strategies and create a more supportive learning environment. Extensive	3.80
3	Teachers understand their learners' cultural beliefs can create learning experiences that are more relevant and engaging. Extensive	4.00
4	Teachers are sensitive to their learners' cultural behaviors can adapt their teaching style and communication approach to be more effective. Moderately Extensive	3.20
5	Teachers incorporate cultural artifacts into their teaching can help their learners to appreciate and understand different cultures, and can create a more inclusive and welcoming learning environment. Moderately Extensive	2.85
	Overall Mean Moderately Extensive	3.28

Lai and Kwan (2020) explored the impact of cultural background on the teaching practices of primary school teachers in Hong Kong. The study found that teachers' cultural background can impact their teaching practices, particularly in terms of their use of language and their approach to discipline. The findings suggest that teachers' cultural background can impact their teaching practices, which can in turn impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Huang and Li (2020) explored the impact of cultural background on the social development of kinder learners in China. The study found that kinder learners who had a more diverse cultural background were more likely to have

positive attitudes towards diversity and to engage in more positive social behaviors. The findings suggest that teachers need to be aware of the cultural background of their kinder learners to provide effective socio-emotional support. Teachers who come from different cultural backgrounds may have different teaching styles, beliefs, and values that can impact their interactions with kindergarten students. Teachers who come from different cultural backgrounds may have unique teaching styles, beliefs, and values that can impact the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. A study by Gadiana and Rarangol (2018) explored the impact of teachers' cultural background on their teach-

ing practices. The study found that teachers who come from different cultural backgrounds may have different teaching styles and practices, which can impact the academic outcomes of kindergarten students. The findings suggest that teachers' cultural background plays a critical role in shaping the quality of teacher-kinder learner interaction. Children who experience social-emotional difficulties may struggle with forming positive relationships with others, regulating their emotions, and coping with stress. This is especially important in the context of rural areas, where kinder learners may have limited access to resources and services. Kinder learners who develop strong social-emotional skills are more likely to have positive relationships with peers and teachers, perform well academically, and have a positive sense of self. Zhang and Johnson (2018) explored the relationship between social-emotional development and school readiness in kinder learners in rural China. The study found that kinder learners from rural areas showed lower levels of social-emotional development than their urban counterparts. The study also found that family socioeconomic status and parental involvement in

education were important predictors of social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas. Table 7 shows the summary of the extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: communication style (3.59); teaching strategies (3.47), classroom environment (3.45) is often-times manifested. while student's temperament (3.34); cultural background (3.28) and teacher's attitude and personality (3.24) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.39 denotes extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Strategies for Enhancing Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction in Rural Areas To enhance teacher-kinder learner interaction in rural areas, several strategies can be employed. One of the most effective strategies is the provision of training and professional development opportunities for teachers. According to Sallis, Probert and Hebron (2019), teacher training and development programs improve the skills and knowledge of teachers, thus enabling them to deliver quality education to learners.

In conclusion, the teacher-kinder learner interaction is critical in the education process, particularly in rural areas. The interaction helps to create an enabling learning environment, improve academic performance, and prepare learners for life beyond their immediate environment. However, several challenges hinder effective interaction in rural areas, including the shortage of qualified teachers and limited infrastructure. To enhance teacher-kinder learner interaction in rural areas, strategies such as training and professional development for teachers and the use of technology can be employed.

Social-emotional Development among Kinder Learners

Social-emotional development is an impor-

tant aspect of a kinder learner's overall development. Children who experience social-emotional difficulties may struggle with forming positive relationships with others, regulating their emotions, and coping with stress. This is especially important in the context of rural areas, where kinder learners may have limited access to resources and services. Kinder learners who develop strong social-emotional skills are more likely to have positive relationships with peers and teachers, perform well academically, and have a positive sense of self. However, there is limited research on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas, where unique contextual factors may impact development.

Table 9. Extent of Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction

No	Extent of Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction Descriptive Equivalent	Mean
1	Communication Style Extensive	3.59
2	Student’s Temperament Moderately Extensive	3.34
3	Classroom Environment Extensive	3.45
4	Teaching Strategies Moderately Extensive	3.47
5	Teacher’s Attitude And Personality Moderately Extensive	3.24
6	Cultural Background Moderately Extensive	3.28
	Overall Mean Moderately	3.39

Table 8 shows the extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of family environment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Cultural background have different expectations for child-rearing, socialization, and emotional expression, which can impact a child’s social-emotional development (3.47), Children from lower SES families experience more stress, instability, and adversity than children from higher SES families, which can impact their social-emotional development (3.45) and Children from single-parent families or blended families have different social-emotional needs and experiences than children

from traditional two-parent families (3.41) are oftentimes manifested, while, Children feel secure, loved, and supported by their families are more likely to develop positive social-emotional skills, such as empathy, self-regulation, and resilience (3.24) and Parenting style such as authoritarian, authoritative, permissive, or neglectful, can have a significant impact on a child’s social-emotional development (3.41) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.34 denotes extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of family environment is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Family environment is a crucial component of a child’s social-emotional development, and it plays an important role in shaping a kinder learner’s personality and behavior. In rural areas, kinder learners may face unique challenges that can impact their social-emotional development. A study by Choudhury et al. (2020) examined the impact of family environment on the social-emotional development of

kinder learners in rural areas in Bangladesh. The study found that kinder learners in rural areas who have positive family environments were more likely to have higher levels of social-emotional development than those with negative family environments. The findings suggest that family environment plays a critical role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas in

Table 10. Extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of family environment

No	Family Environment	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Parenting style such as authoritarian, authoritative, permissive, or neglectful, can have a significant impact on a child’s social-emotional development.	3.19	Moderately Extensive
2	Children from single-parent families or blended families have different social-emotional needs and experiences than children from traditional two-parent families.	3.41	Extensive
3	Children from lower SES families experience more stress, instability, and adversity than children from higher SES families, which can impact their social-emotional development.	3.45	Extensive
4	Cultural background have different expectations for child-rearing, socialization, and emotional expression, which can impact a child’s social-emotional development.	3.47	Extensive
5	Children feel secure, loved, and supported by their families are more likely to develop positive social-emotional skills, such as empathy, self-regulation, and resilience.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.34	Moderately Extensive

Bangladesh. Chen et al. (2019) examined the role of parental warmth and control in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural China. The study found that parental warmth had a positive impact on kinder learners’ social-emotional development, while parental control had a negative impact. The findings suggest that parental warmth, rather than control, may be more effective in promoting kinder learners’ social-emotional development in rural areas. O’Hara et al. (2022) investigated the impact of parental involvement in kinder learners’ social-emotional development in rural Australia. The study found that parental involvement, including parent-child communication and parental support, was positively associated with kinder learners’ social-emotional development. The findings suggest that parental involvement can be a critical factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas. Social-emotional development is a crucial aspect of a child’s overall development, and it can be influenced by vari-

ous factors, including the family environment. In rural areas of the Philippines, kinder learners may face unique challenges that can impact their social-emotional development.

Table 9 shows the extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of peer relationship. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Children from different cultural backgrounds may have different expectations and norms for social interaction, which can impact their ability to form positive relationships with peers from different backgrounds (4.47) and Children who have strong social skills are more likely to develop positive peer relationships, while children who struggle with social skills may be at greater risk for peer rejection and social isolation (4.45) are always manifested, while, Children who have positive, supportive friendships with peers are more likely to develop positive social-emotional skills, while children who experience social rejection or exclusion may be at greater risk for

emotional and behavioral problems (4.41) and Children who engage in imaginative, cooperative play are more likely to develop prosocial behaviors, while children who engage in competitive or aggressive play may be at greater risk for behavior problems (4.19) are oftentimes manifested, and Children who experience bullying may develop low self-esteem, anxiety, depression, and other emotional and behavioral problems (3.24) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.15 denotes extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of peer relationship is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Peer relationships play a critical role in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners. However, kinder learners in rural areas may face unique challenges in developing positive peer relationships. A study by Aljohani et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between peer relationships and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of Saudi Arabia.

The study found that positive peer relationships, including positive social interactions and social support, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. Zheng and Xie (2019) examined the relationship between peer relationships and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of China. The study found that positive peer relationships, including social support and peer acceptance, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. Singh et al. (2022) investigated the role of peer relationships in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of India. The study found that positive peer relationships, including social support and positive social interactions, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive peer relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of India.

Table 11. Extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of peer relationship

No	Peer Relationship	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Children who engage in imaginative, cooperative play are more likely to develop prosocial behaviors, while children who engage in competitive or aggressive play may be at greater risk for behavior problems.	4.19	Extensive
2	Children who have positive, supportive friendships with peers are more likely to develop positive social-emotional skills, while children who experience social rejection or exclusion may be at greater risk for emotional and behavioral problems.	4.41	Extensive
3	Children who have strong social skills are more likely to develop positive peer relationships, while children who struggle with social skills may be at greater risk for peer rejection and social isolation.	4.45	Very Extensive
4	Children from different cultural backgrounds may have different expectations and norms for social interaction, which can impact their ability to form positive relationships with peers from different backgrounds.	4.47	Very Extensive
5	Children who experience bullying may develop low self-esteem, anxiety, depression, and other emotional and behavioral problems.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	4.15	Extensive

Mendoza and Fajardo (2020) examined the impact of peer relationships on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in

rural areas of the Philippines. The study found that positive peer relationships, including social support, peer acceptance, and positive so-

cial interactions, were positively associated with kinder learners’ social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive peer relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the Philippines. Peer relationships are a critical component of promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas. It is essential for schools in rural areas to provide opportunities for kinder learners to develop positive peer relationships and to support those who may face unique challenges in these areas.

Table 10 shows the extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of teacher-student relationship. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Teachers who develop a strong relationship with their students establish trust and respect with them which means that students feel comfortable talking to their teachers and sharing their

thoughts and feelings (4.50), Teachers provide positive feedback and encouragement help students feel confident in their abilities, helps them to develop a growth mindset and a desire to learn and improve (4.47) and Teachers provide emotional support create a safe and nurturing environment for their students, when students feel emotionally secure, they are better able to focus on their learning and development (4.45) are always manifested, while, Teachers communicate clearly and regularly with their students help them feel valued and supported (3.50) is oftentimes manifested, and Teachers actively engage with their students in meaningful ways foster a positive relationship show interest in their students’ lives, participate in their learning experiences, and create a sense of community in the classroom (3.24) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.03 denotes extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of peer relationship is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 12. Extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of teacher-student relationship

No	Teacher-Student Relationship	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Teachers who develop a strong relationship with their students establish trust and respect with them which means that students feel comfortable talking to their teachers and sharing their thoughts and feelings.	4.50	Very Extensive
2	Teachers communicate clearly and regularly with their students help them feel valued and supported.	3.50	Extensive
3	Teachers provide emotional support create a safe and nurturing environment for their students, when students feel emotionally secure, they are better able to focus on their learning and development.	4.45	Very Extensive
4	Teachers provide positive feedback and encouragement help students feel confident in their abilities, helps them to develop a growth mindset and a desire to learn and improve.	4.47	Very Extensive
5	Teachers actively engage with their students in meaningful ways foster a positive relationship show interest in their students’ lives, participate in their learning experiences, and create a sense of community in the classroom.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	4.03	Extensive

The relationship between teachers and students is a critical component of social-emotional development among kinder learners. In rural areas, where resources and support may be limited, the teacher-student relationship may play an even more significant role in promoting positive social-emotional development among kinder learners. A study by Maldonado-Carreño et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between teacher-student relationships and social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of Mexico. The study found that positive teacher-student relationships, including emotional support, academic support, and positive feedback, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. Wang et al. (2019) examined the impact of teacher-student relationships on the social-emotional development of kinder learners in rural areas of China. The study found that positive teacher-student relationships, including teacher warmth, trust, and communication, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive teacher-student relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the international setting. Kaya and Goktas (2022) investigated the role of teacher-student relationships in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of Turkey. The study found that positive teacher-student relationships, including emotional support, academic support, and positive feedback, were positively associated with kinder learners' social-emotional development. The findings suggest that positive teacher-student relationships can be an essential factor in promoting social-emotional development among kinder learners in rural areas of the international setting. Tan (2020), the impact of teacher-student relationships on the academic

performance of kinder learners in a rural school in the Philippines was investigated. The findings showed that a positive relationship was associated with better academic outcomes, including higher grades and test scores. The study identified several factors that influenced this relationship, including the teacher's enthusiasm, encouragement, and support.

Table 11 shows the extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of classroom environment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Personalization means that teachers tailor their teaching to the individual needs and interests of their students and feel that their learning is meaningful and relevant, they are more likely to engage in the learning process and develop positive attitudes towards school (4.75) is always manifested, while, Teachers create a positive climate foster a sense of community and promote positive interactions between students (3.55) and Teachers establish clear expectations for behavior and learning help students understand what is expected of them and promote a sense of structure and predictability, which can reduce anxiety and promote positive behavior (3.55) are oftentimes manifested, and Teachers provide opportunities for students to interact with one another help them develop social skills and establish positive relationships (3.17) and The physical environment of a classroom can impact the social and emotional development of kindergarten students, thus, a well-organized, clean, and comfortable classroom can help students feel calm and focused (3.15) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.63 denotes extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of classroom environment is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 13. Extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of classroom environment

No	Classroom Environment Descriptive Equivalent	Mean
1	Teachers create a positive climate foster a sense of community and promote positive interactions between students. Extensive	3.55
2	The physical environment of a classroom can impact the social and emotional development of kindergarten students, thus, a well-organized, clean, and comfortable classroom can help students feel calm and focused. Moderately Extensive	3.15
3	Teachers establish clear expectations for behavior and learning help students understand what is expected of them and promote a sense of structure and predictability, which can reduce anxiety and promote positive behavior. Extensive	3.55
4	Teachers provide opportunities for students to interact with one another help them develop social skills and establish positive relationships. Moderately Extensive	3.17
5	Personalization means that teachers tailor their teaching to the individual needs and interests of their students and feel that their learning is meaningful and relevant, they are more likely to engage in the learning process and develop positive attitudes towards school. Very Extensive	4.75
	Overall Mean Extensive	3.63

The classroom environment can affect the emotional well-being of the students and influence their academic performance. One study conducted by Sabino and Delos Santos (2018) explored the relationship between classroom environment and the social-emotional development of kinder learners in a rural school in the Philippines. The study found that a positive classroom environment, which includes a comfortable and organized classroom setting, promotes positive attitudes among kinder learners towards school and their teachers. It also fosters a sense of belongingness and acceptance among kinder learners. Adarlo and Quebral (2019) investigated the relationship between classroom environment and the social-emotional development of kinder learners in a rural school. The study found that classroom environment significantly affects the self-esteem of kinder learners. In a study conducted by Garcia (2020), the relationship between classroom environment and academic performance among kinder learners in a rural school in the Philippines was examined. The study found that the classroom environment significantly influenced the academic performance of kinder learners. Such a classroom environment can promote positive attitudes towards school and peers, and foster a sense of belongingness and acceptance among the learners. Teachers should therefore design their classroom environment in a way that is

conductive to the social-emotional development of the learners.

Table 12 shows the extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of personal temperament. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Children are self-aware are better able to recognize their strengths and weaknesses, which can help them develop a positive sense of self-esteem (3.60) is oftentimes manifested, Children have a high activity level may be more prone to impulsive behavior and may need additional support to develop self-control. Conversely, children with a low activity level may need more opportunities for movement and physical activity (2.75), Children regulate their emotions are better able to cope with stress, frustration, and disappointment (2.55) and Children demonstrate social competence are able to establish and maintain positive relationships with peers and adults (2.15) are sometimes manifested, while, Children have a longer attention span are better able to engage in learning activities and complete tasks (2.17) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.64 denotes extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of personal temperament is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Several studies have explored this relationship in the Philippine context. For instance, Carabelle et al. (2018) investigated the relation-

ship between personal temperament and social-emotional development among Kinder learners in a rural community. They found that certain

Table 14. Extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of personal temperament (Table 12)

No	Personal Temperament Descriptive Equivalent	Mean
1	Children regulate their emotions are better able to cope with stress, frustration, and disappointment. Moderately Extensive	2.55
2	Children demonstrate social competence are able to establish and maintain positive relationships with peers and adults. Moderately Extensive	2.15
3	Children are self-aware are better able to recognize their strengths and weaknesses, which can help them develop a positive sense of self-esteem. Extensive	3.60
4	Children have a longer attention span are better able to engage in learning activities and complete tasks. Less Extensive	2.17
5	Children have a high activity level may be more prone to impulsive behavior and may need additional support to develop self-control. Conversely, children with a low activity level may need more opportunities for movement and physical activity. Moderately Extensive	2.75
	Overall Mean	2.64
	Moderately Extensive	

temperaments, such as being easy-going and adaptable, were associated with higher levels of social-emotional development. Similarly, Melendres et al. (2019) examined the relationship between temperament, emotion regulation, and social competence among Kinder learners in a rural school. They found that high levels of activity and low levels of adaptability were negatively associated with social competence. Moreover, emotion regulation mediated the relationship between temperament and social competence. Reyes et al. (2020) explored the relationship between temperament, parental responsiveness, and social-emotional competence among Kinder learners in rural areas. They found that parental responsiveness played a moderating role in the relationship between temperament

and social-emotional competence. Specifically, children with difficult temperaments exhibited higher social-emotional competence when their parents were highly responsive.

Table 13 shows the summary of the extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: peer relationship (4.15), teacher-student relationship (4.03) and classroom environment (3.63) are oftentimes extensive, while, family environment (3.34) and personal temperament (2.64) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.55 denotes extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 15. Summary of the Extent of Social-Emotional Development among Kinder Learners

No	Extent of Social-Emotional Development among Kinder Learners	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Family Environment	3.34	Moderately Extensive
2	Peer Relationship	4.15	Extensive
3	Teacher-student Relationship	4.03	Extensive
4	Classroom Environment	3.63	Extensive
5	Personal Temperament	2.64	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.55	Extensive

Note. This table summarizes the extent of social-emotional development among kindergarten learners. Descriptive equivalent refers to the interpretation of the mean score.

Relationship Between Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction and Social-Emotional Development among Kinder Learners

It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between teacher-kinder learner interaction ($r=0.878$; $p<.001$) and social-emotional development among kinder learners Table 14 revealed the yielded results of the significant correlation between teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development among kinder learners. It provides an information that the

posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development among kinder learners must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results. The relationship between teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development among kinder learners is a critical aspect of early childhood education. Teachers play a significant role in fostering positive social-emotional development in their students.

Table 16. Significant Relationship between teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development among kinder learners

Variables	teacher-kinder learner interaction		Interpretation	Decision
	r-value	p-value		
social-emotional development	0.878	<0.001	Significant	Reject H_0

**significant @ $p < 0.05$.*

Adarlo and Quebral (2019) said that teachers who foster a secure attachment with their kinder learners can help them feel safe and secure in the classroom, which can positively affect their social-emotional development. When children feel safe and secure, they are more likely to explore their environment and form positive relationships with others. Children who have secure attachments with their teachers also tend to have better emotional regulation skills, are more resilient, and have higher self-esteem. Mendoza (2018) stated that teachers who model positive behaviors, such as empathy, kindness, and respect, can teach their kinder learners how to behave positively towards others. When children see their teacher modeling these behaviors, they are more likely to emulate them, which can lead to positive social-emotional development. Kaya and Goktas (2022) said that teachers who provide opportunities for children to interact with one another can help them develop social skills such as cooperation, communication, and problem-solving. When children have these skills, they are more likely to form positive relationships with their peers and have better social-emotional development. Delos Reyes and Patacsil (2022) shared that teachers who create a supportive classroom environment that values each child’s unique strengths and needs can positively impact their social-emotional development. When children feel

supported and valued, they are more likely to develop positive self-esteem and self-concept. Finally, effective communication between teachers and kinder learners is essential for positive social-emotional development. Teachers who communicate effectively with their students can help them understand and regulate their emotions, which can positively impact their social-emotional development. Teachers who listen to their students, acknowledge their feelings, and respond appropriately can help their students develop healthy emotional regulation skills.

Indicators of Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction that Significantly Influence Social-Emotional Development among Kinder Learners

Table 15 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the indicators of teacher-kinder learner interaction that significantly influence social-emotional development among kinder learners. Indicators of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style (0.008), classroom environment (0.003), teaching strategies (0.005) and teacher attitude and personality (0.003) significantly influence social-emotional development among kinder learners, while students’ temperament (0.540) and cultural background (0.585) do not influence social-emotional development among kinder learners.

Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.869 suggests that the indicators of teacher-kinder learner interaction explained 86.9%. In addition, the F-value

shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (225.896) and F-statistic is

Table 17. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Teacher-Kinder Learner Interaction that Significantly Influence Social-Emotional Development Among Kinder Learners

Model		B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value
Decision					
H (Intercept)		4.145	0.069	60.416	0.001
4.145					
H (Intercept)		0.201	0.185	1.086	0.280
0.201					
0.315	Communication Style	0.108	0.107	0.102	1.010
	*Reject H0				
0.196	Student's Temperament	0.440	0.108	0.136	1.299
	0.540	Accept H0			
0.038	Classroom Environment	0.203	0.097	0.210	2.098
	0.003	*Reject H0			
0.001	Teaching Strategies	0.485	0.086	0.499	5.654
	0.485	*Reject H0			
0.028	Teacher Attitude and Personality	0.204	0.096	0.220	2.078
	0.003	*Reject H0			
0.001	Cultural Background	0.485	0.086	0.499	5.654
	0.585	Accept H0			
R ²					
= 0.869					
F-value					
= 225.896					
p-value					
= ;0.002					

significant $p_i.002$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of Instructional Delivery. Bandura's social learning theory emphasizes the role of observational learning, or learning by observing others, in shaping human behavior. Bandura's social learning theory has important implications for the social-emotional development of kindergarten learners. Teachers are influential models for young children, and their behavior and interactions with students can shape the social-emotional skills and behaviors of their students. By providing positive role models and demonstrating appropriate social behaviors, teachers can help their students develop important social skills, such as empathy, coop-

eration, and emotional regulation. Research has supported the importance of teacher-learner interactions in supporting the social-emotional development of young children. Hamre and Pianta (2005) found that positive teacher-student relationships were associated with better social-emotional outcomes for students. Another study by Denham and colleagues (2012) found that teacher emotional support was positively related to children's social-emotional competence. By understanding the importance of observational learning and the influence of teachers as role models, educators can work to create positive learning environments that support the social-emotional development of young children.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

5.1. Findings—The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions. The teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style (3.59); teaching strategies (3.47), classroom environment (3.45) is oftentimes manifested. while student's temperament (3.34); cultural background (3.28) and teacher's attitude and personality (3.24) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.39 denotes extent of teacher-kinder learner interaction is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of peer relationship (4.15), teacher-student relationship (4.03) and classroom environment (3.63) are oftentimes extensive, while, family environment (3.34) and personal temperament (2.64) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.55 denotes extent of social-emotional development among kinder learners is oftentimes manifested,

thus, extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teacher-kinder learner interaction ($r=0.878$; $p_i.001$) and social-emotional development among kinder learners. Indicators of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style (0.008), classroom environment (0.003), teaching strategies (0.005) and teacher attitude and personality (0.003) significantly influenced social-emotional development among kinder learners, while students' temperament (0.540) and cultural background (0.585) do not influence social-emotional development among kinder learners.

5.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style, teaching strategies, classroom environment, student's temperament, cultural background and teacher's attitude and denotes extent of teacher-

kinder learner interaction is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The social-emotional development among kinder learners in terms of peer relationship, teacher-student relationship, classroom environment, family environment and personal temperament denotes oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. There is a significant correlation between teacher-kinder learner interaction and social-emotional development among kinder learners. Indicators of teacher-kinder learner interaction in terms of communication style, classroom environment, teaching strategies and teacher attitude and personality significantly influenced social-emotional development among kinder learners.

5.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; To The Public School District Supervisor. May provide professional development opportunities for teachers to learn about best practices in fostering positive social emotional development among kinder learners. Allocate resources to ensure that classrooms have a positive and supportive environment for kinder learners. Support research efforts that explore the impact of teacher-kinder learner interaction on social-emotional development. To The School Principal. May encourage teachers to use developmentally appropriate

teaching strategies and create a positive classroom environment that fosters social-emotional development among kinder learners. Provide resources to support teachers in creating a positive classroom environment and implementing effective teaching strategies. Recognize and reward teachers who foster positive social-emotional development among kinder learners. To The Teachers. May foster a positive and supportive classroom environment that values diversity, encourages cooperation and collaboration, and provides opportunities for play and exploration. Communicate effectively and positively with kinder learners, acknowledging their feelings and responding appropriately. Use developmentally appropriate teaching strategies that promote social-emotional development, such as storytelling, role-playing, and social problem-solving activities. To The Future Researchers. May conduct longitudinal studies to explore the long-term impact of teacher-kinder learner interaction on social-emotional development. Investigate the impact of different teaching strategies on social-emotional development among kinder learners. Conduct research that explores the impact of classroom environment and teacher attitude and personality on social-emotional development among kinder learners.

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